

“A COMPARATIVE CLINICAL STUDY OF LODHRA CHURNA LEPA AND VACHA CHURNA LEPA IN YUVANA PIDIKA W.S.R. TO ACNE VULGARIS”

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ABSTRACT

Yuvana Pidika is one among those diseases in adolescent age which occurs in the golden period of life and then may affect the self esteem of particular affected individual. Taking in account, the signs and symptoms of Yuvana Pidika, it can be taken as “Acne vulgaris” according to modern view. Vitiation of Vata and Kapha dosha along with Rakta dhatu is seen in Yuvana Pidika. In the present study the efficacy of Lodhra Churna Lepa is compared Vacha Churna Lepa in the management of Yuvana Pidika. It was a comparative clinical study wherein 30 patients were selected and divided into two Groups namely, Group A, and Group B each consisting of 15 patients. Group A was treated with Lodhra Churna Lepa. Group B was treated with Vacha Churna Lepa. Follow up was done on 30th day and 60th day of the course. For the assessment of the results grading of 1st day, 30th day and 60th day was used. P-Values for all parameters are more than 0.05 except for the

parameters Kandu, Number of Pidaka and Shotha. Hence it can be said that statistically there

is no significant difference between Group A. Lodhra Churna Lepa and Group B Vacha Churna Lepa in the management of Yuvana Pidika. Average percentage of improvement of Group B is 51.05% which is greater than Average percentage of improvement of Group A-44.89%. Hence, we conclude that effect observed in Group B is more than Group A.

KEYWORDS: Yuvana Pidika, Lodhra Churna Lepa, Vacha Churna Lepa, Acne Vulgaris.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal medicine, sometimes referred to as herbalism or Botanical medicine, is the use of herbs for their therapeutic or medicinal value. An herb is a plant or plant part valued for its medicinal, aromatic or savory qualities. Herb plants produce and contain a variety of chemical substance that act upon the body. It was the period of Nighantus the botanical description of the medicinal herbs came into description. Vacha (*Acorus calamus* L.) is exceedingly influential and renowned drug in Ayurveda well known for medhya karma (that which improve memory & intellect). The rhizome of this plant has been indicated as brain tonic in weak memory (API). In Sanskrit the word Vacha means that which improves speech or enhances the power of speech. It is commonly known as Sweet flag, a tall perennial wetland monocot plant from the Araceae family. It is exceedingly common in Manipur and Naga Hills and on the edges of lakes & streams. It is found throughout India under cultivation as well as in the wild state, in plains, lower elevations and in Himalayan upto altitude of 2200 ml. Vacha has a special place in Ayurveda as it is a main Medhya drug, which has the property of improving the memory power and intellect. Poor memory, lower retention and slow recall are common problems in today's stressful and competitive world. Age, stress, emotions are conditions that may led to memory loss, amnesia, anxiety, high blood pressure, dementia and to more ominous threat like schizophrenia and Alzheimer's diseases. Vacha (*Acorus calamus* Linn.), an indigenous drug of India belongs to family Acoraceae. It is delineated under various therapeutical groups like Lekhaneeya", Triptighna", Arshoghna dashemani" etc., by Acharya Charaka, Pippalyadi, Vachadi etc., ganas by Acharya Sushruta and Mustadi, Vatsakadi etc., gana by Vagbhata. The pharmacognostical characters of Vacha are described through various synonyms like Shadgrantha (Having six nodes), Uragandha (Having strong aroma), Lomasha (Having small hairs), Golomi (Having small hairs like cow) etc. It has important pharmacological properties like Deepana (Appetizer), Pachana (Digestive), Vamaka (Emetic), Medhya (brain tonic), Kanthya (Good for throat), Sanjnanasthapana (Restores lost conciousness), Vedanasthapana (Anodyne) etc., and hence

used extensively in therapeutics. The skin is often referred to as the largest body organ and serves as the main protective barrier against damage to internal tissues from trauma, ultraviolet light, temperature, toxins and bacteria. Changes in the skin color may indicate homeostatic imbalance in the body. Everyone wants to look his/her face beautiful, clean and attractive. Even a small spot on the face especially of younger ones causes worry. Acne is the scourge of mankind and the travesty of youth. Some consider acne to be merely a cosmetic problem, but it may have significant and enduring emotional and psychological effects. Acne affects skin of the face, the upper part of the chest and the back. Acne vulgaris is self-limited disorder primarily in teenagers and young adult, although perhaps 10 to 20% of adults may continue to experience same form of disease. People are spending a lot of time and money to restore skin to a more normal or youthful appearance. One such derma condition is Yuvana pidika affecting in young age, with acne eruption, post acne marks etc. Yuvana pidika occurs when pores of the skin become clogged with oil, dead skin cells, and bacteria changing diet habit or moving from healthy diet to unhealthy diet or lifestyle exposure to polluted environment and sweating can also make the condition worse. strong soap, hard scrubbing, and pricking at pimples can make acne worse. According to Ayurveda, Classics Acharya Sushruta has mentioned that in Yuvavastha due to prakopa of khapa, vata and rakta, shalmali kantak like pidakas arises. These pidikas are called as Yuvana pidika. The common site of acne vulgaris is face and particularly the skin of cheeks, lower jaw, nose, chin, forehead are affected and also seen in neck, chest, shoulder and back. Acne is almost ubiquitous in the teenage years, differences between individuals being a matter of severity of disease and facility with which scarring develops, peak severity is in the late teenage years but Acne may persist into the third decade and both sex are equally affected beyond, particularly in female. In modern cosmetology the treatment of Acne depends on the grade and severity of Acne. In topical treatment, the topical retinoids like adapalene, tretinoin etc., are used. Topical antibiotics for Acne include erythromycin and clindamycin or in combination with benzoyl peroxide and some lipophilic antibiotics such as doxycycline and minocycline are used which usually cause adverse effect like skin irritation, peeling, redness and associated with sun sensitivity. Hence it is a need of hour to take over a study on such a disease, which is affecting most of the adolescents in their personality developing period and as it has been redefined towards as chronic disease instead of simple and self-limiting disease. Here in this study, Lepa karma has been taken even though other line of treatment like Vamana and Rakta mokshana has been mentioned. There are many researches carried out in different institutions on Yuvana pidika, where Vamana and Rakthamokshana line of treatment were adopted and

got satisfactory results. So, for our study we have chosen Lepa line of treatment. There are so many Lepas explained for Yuvana pidika in Ayurvedic classics as treatment modality which acts quickly and locally. In the current study, Yogratnakara had explained Sidharthakadi Lepa in Utrardha, Chikitsya parkaranam (4th sloka) which includes 4 ingredients i.e., Sidharthaka, Vacha, Lodhra and Sandhava. Out of the above 4 ingredients, here is a small effort to try the efficacy of two ingredients, one is Lodhra churna and other is Vacha churna as lepa/ pralepa in Yuvana pidika for external application in my dissertation work.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ayurveda is an established medical system, which has been developed by various ancient Acharyas after rigorous experiments and examinations.

But today it's necessary to prove the Ayurvedic facts on the modern parameters, without altering its basic structure as Methodical approach is the backbone of research. Research is a scientific study through which one can establish new facts, discarding the old facts or modifying the present facts. Before starting any research work it is necessary to list out the material required and the methods used for research. These are explained below. Research Approach: In the present study, the main objective was to compare efficacy of Lodhra Churna Lepa and Vacha Churna Lepa in Yuvana pidika. The efficacy was determined by finding out the difference between the baseline data of the parameters to the post medication data. Study design: A Simple comparative clinical Prospective study and sampling technique is purposive or deliberate. Sample size and grouping: 30 patients suffering from Yuvana pidika were selected and divided into 2 groups, 15 patients in each group.

Group A- 15 patients were applied externally with Lodhra Churna Lepa for 30 days.

Group B- 15 patients were applied externally with Vacha Churna Lepa Arogyavardhini Vati for 30 days Source of Data: Patient suffering from Yuvana pidika were selected from Kayachikitsa and Panchkarma O.P.D and I.P.D. of R.G.E.S. A.M.C & Hospital, Ron, after fulfilling the Inclusion and Exclusion criteria.

SELECTION CRITERIA: The cases were selected strictly as per the pre-set inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria: Patient age group between 12 to 30 years irrespective of sex, religion, socioeconomic status and occupation were taken. Patients presenting with signs & symptoms of Yuvana pidika (acne vulgaris). Patients who were fit for Lepa karma.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients having pidika other than face and other kshudraroga and kustaroga. Pidika produced due to side effect of any drug applied earlier. Patients who were contraindicated for lepa karma mentioned in classical texts. The patients suffering from systemic pathologies. Patients suffering from Diabetes Mellitus. Patients aged below 12 years and above 30 years. Acne due to malignant cases. Acne due to anti-tubercular drugs.

Criteria for diagnosis: Diagnosis was established by clinical examination of signs and symptoms of Yuvana pidika as follows: 1. Shalmali kantaka Sadrusha Pidaka. 2. Saruja 3. Srava 4. Ghana Shotha 5. Vedana 6. Kandu 7. Paka 8. Vivarnyata Investigations: a) HB% b) TLC c) DLC d) VDRL (If necessary) (e) AEC (f) RBS.

INTERVENTIONS: GROUP A-: Lodhra Churna Lepa Mode: In morning time per day- External application of lepa on pidakas. Duration: 30 days. Follow up: 30 days Method: Lodhra Churna was mixed with water and applied as lepa over the face of thickness of 1/2 Angula (0.88 cm) in morning (between 7 To 10 am). Lepa was kept on face till it dries, then it was washed with warm water. GROUP B-: Vacha Churna Lepa Mode: In morning time per day- External application of lepa on pidakas. Duration: 30 days Follow up: 30 Days.

OBJECTIVES

1. To evaluate the efficacy of Lodhra Churna lepa in Yuvana pidika.
2. To evaluate the efficacy of Vacha Churna lepa in Yuvana pidika.
3. To compare the effect of Lodhra Churna Lepa and Vacha Churna lepa in Yuvana pidika.

ASSESSMENT OF THE RESULTS: The subjective and objective parameters of base line data to post medication were compared for assessment of the results. All the result were analyzed statistically for 'p' value using paired - T Test and ANOVA.

ASSESSMENT PARAMETERS: Subjective Parameters:- 1. Kandu 2. Vedna 3. Daha Objective Parameters:- 1. Number of Pidika 2. Area Occupied By Pidika 3. Shotha 4. Srava 5. Paka 6. Vivarnyata.

RESULTS

1. Treatment Result on Vedana so it can be concluded that the effect of both groups were having equal effect in treating the Yuvana Pidika. But percentage improvement of Group-B (38.75%) was more than of group-A (34.78%).

2. Showing Comparison Between Two Groups for Kandru, so it can be concluded that the effect of both the groups was having equal effect in treating the Yuvana Pidika. But percentage improvement of Group B (51.81%) was more than of group A (46.94%)
3. Shotha, so it can be concluded that the effect of both groups significant effect in treating the Yuvana Pidika. Percentage improvement of Group B (57.8%) was more than of group A (48.11%)
4. Paaka, so it can be concluded that the effect of both the groups was having equal effect in treating the Yuvana Pidika. But percentage improvement of Group B (50%) was more than of group A (45.45%)
5. Vivarnyata - so it can be concluded that the effect of both the groups was having equal effect in treating the Yuvana Pidika. But percentage improvement of Group B (50%) was more than of group A (45.45%)

DISCUSSION

The present study entitled “A Comparative Clinical Study of Lodhra Churna Lepa and Vacha Churna Lepa in the management of Yuvana Pidika W. S. R. to Acne Vulgaris” was carried out on 30 patients assigned into two Groups viz., Group A & Group B respectively. Patients in Group A were subjected to Lodhra Churna Lepa whereas patients in Group B were subjected to Vacha Churna Lepa. Science is the only media to observe and analyze the all kinds of events in the universe. The systematic arrangement of facts and events, ascertained by observations and interpretation makes the facts a part of the science. Discussions on the study are made under the following headings: 1. Discussion on disease 2. Discussion on Clinical study 3. Probable mode of action of Lodhra Churna Lepa 4. Probable mode of action of Vacha Churna Lepa Discussion On Disease Yuvana Pidika is one of such disease which massacres the beauty of the skin. The site and the period of the occurrence of this disease are face and adolescent respectively. The age of occurrence of this problem such that the beauty consciousness a person is at its peak and the site of this disease is such that is sufferer is in more trouble as it cannot be kept covered all the time. Since medicine has its origin in the desire to provide human treatment for other human beings, it follows the ethical principles, play a fundamental role in the provision of medical care. Medicine is only in part the application of the knowledge about social and behavioral processes.

Unlike the basic physical and biological sciences, medicine

CONCLUSION

Clinical observations and Discussion the following conclusions may be drawn.¹ In the present study, Lodhra Churna Lepa and Vacha Churna Lepa both the groups are having significant result in managing the Yuvana Pidika with p value < 0.05 . Statistically there is no significant difference in the mean effect of Group A Lodhra Churna Lepa and Group B Vacha Churna Lepa in the management of Yuvana Pidika with p value >0.05 in all the assessment parameters except Kandu, Shotha and Number of Pidaka. Comparatively, Vacha Churna Lepa (Group B) (overall effect 51.05%) has shown better results than Lodhra Churna Lepa (Group A) (overall effect 44.89%). The incidence rate of disease is more in the age group of 16-20 years (67.5%) hence it is called as Yavana Pidaka. The incidence rate of disease is more in Females when compared with Males as the early hormonal changes are seen in females. Yuvana Pidika in modern view has similarity with Acne Vulgaris which is called to be a Physically and Psychologically scarring disease. The Quality-of-life scales have assessed that the impact of Acne is as similar as Epilepsy or Asthma and redefined it as chronic disease instead of simple and selflimiting. In this disease patients have greater impairment in mental health and associated with psychological disturbances like embracement, anxiety. In the study many of the patients had manasika lakshanas like krodha, ayasa, shoka, which aggravates vata dosha. The reoccurrence was seen in relieved patients who were not following the post operative regimens and probably requires another course of treatment In the line of treatment of Kshudra rogas, the role of Lepa has been explained by all acharyas and it is explained as the first line of treatment.

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